

WAL Streaming Replication with Quorum-Based Split-Brain Detection for Embedded Databases

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Abstract

We present a high-availability replication system for embedded databases (SQLite-class deployment model) implementing warm standby architecture with WAL streaming, automatic failover, quorum-based split-brain prevention using fencing tokens and epoch-based leadership, multi-phase controlled switchover coordination, and logical replication for selective table sync. The split-brain module uses observer (witness) nodes for quorum: a 3-node cluster (1 primary + 2 standby) requires quorum of 2; a 2-node + 1-observer configuration also achieves quorum of 2. Fencing tokens ensure that write operations from a stale primary are rejected by standbys that have accepted a higher epoch. While WAL-based replication is standard in server databases (PostgreSQL, MySQL), no embedded database (SQLite, DuckDB, LevelDB, RocksDB) provides built-in replication with split-brain detection, fencing tokens, role management, and controlled switchover.

Keywords: WAL Replication, Split-Brain Detection, Fencing Tokens, Embedded Database, High Availability, Quorum, Epoch-Based Leadership

1 1. Background and Prior Art

PostgreSQL Streaming Replication: Full WAL streaming with synchronous/asynchronous modes. Server database requiring separate installation, not embeddable in application process.

MySQL Group Replication: Multi-master with Paxos consensus. Server database.

Litestream: SQLite WAL replication to S3/Azure/GCS. External tool (separate binary), no failover logic, no split-brain detection, no controlled switchover. Continuous backup, not HA.

rqlite: Distributed SQLite using Raft consensus. Wraps SQLite in a Raft layer, adds significant overhead and complexity. Different deployment model (distributed system, not embedded).

Turso/libSQL: SQLite fork with embedded replicas. Cloud-managed replication via Turso platform. No self-hosted split-brain detection or controlled switchover.

LiteFS: FUSE-based SQLite replication by Fly.io. Requires Linux FUSE, not available on all platforms. No quorum-based split-brain prevention.

2 2. Technical Contribution

2.1 2.1 WAL Streaming

WalReplicator on the primary reads WAL entries and streams them to standbys via a custom binary protocol over TCP/TLS. WalApplicator on standbys writes received entries to their local WAL and applies them. Three sync modes:

- **Async:** Primary does not wait for standby acknowledgment. Fastest, risk of data loss on failover.
- **Semi-sync:** Primary waits for at least one standby acknowledgment before confirming commit. Balanced.
- **Sync:** Primary waits for ALL standbys. Safest, highest latency.

2.2 2.2 Split-Brain Detection with Fencing Tokens

```
1 // Every write operation must include a valid fencing token
2 struct FencingTokenPayload {
3     epoch: u64,           // monotonically increasing leadership epoch
4     node_id: Uuid,       // claimed primary
5     token: u64,          // cryptographic token
6 }
```

When a new primary is elected, the epoch is incremented. Standbys track the highest epoch they have seen. If a write arrives with a lower epoch than the standby's current known epoch, the write is rejected. This prevents stale primaries from corrupting data after network partitions heal.

Quorum rules:

- 3 nodes (1P + 2S): quorum = 2 (tolerate 1 failure)
- 5 nodes (1P + 4S): quorum = 3 (tolerate 2 failures)
- Observer nodes (witness-only, no data): participate in voting but hold no data, reducing storage costs for quorum

2.3 2.3 Multi-Phase Controlled Switchover

SwitchoverCoordinator manages planned primary changes:

- **Validation:** Check standby is healthy, replication lag acceptable
- **Quiesce:** Stop accepting new writes on old primary
- **Drain:** Wait for in-flight transactions to complete
- **Sync:** Wait for standby to reach old primary's LSN
- **Promote:** Standby becomes new primary (increment epoch)
- **Demote:** Old primary becomes standby
- **Notify:** Broadcast topology change to all nodes and proxy

Each phase has rollback capability. If any phase fails, the switchover is aborted and the old primary resumes.

2.4 2.4 Role Management

RoleManager tracks node state (Primary, Standby, Candidate) and broadcasts role change events:

```
1 enum RoleChangeEvent {
2     PromotedToPrimary { from: NodeRole, reason: RoleChangeReason },
3     DemotedToStandby { from: NodeRole, reason: RoleChangeReason },
4     BecameCandidate { from: NodeRole },
5 }
```

Role changes trigger proxy reconfiguration (PrimaryTracker updates) ensuring queries are routed to the correct node.

2.5 2.5 LSN Manager

Tracks replication positions for each standby:

- `current_lsn`: Last WAL entry written by primary
- `flushed_lsn`: Last WAL entry flushed to disk
- `replay_lsn`: Last WAL entry applied by standby

The gap between `current_lsn` and `replay_lsn` is the replication lag, used for read-replica routing decisions and switchover readiness checks.

2.6 2.6 Logical Replication

Beyond physical WAL streaming, the system supports logical replication via the `change_log` module: table-specific change capture with vector clock integration, enabling selective table replication and cross-version compatibility.

3 3. Implementation

Implemented in Rust. Module: `replication/` with 15 sub-modules: `wal_replicator`, `wal_applicator`, `failover_watcher`, `lsn_manager`, `transport`, `streaming`, `wal_store`, `split_brain`, `logical_replication`, `query_forwarder`, `role_manager`, `switchover`, `topology`, `ha_state`, `config`. Feature-gated: `ha-tier1`. Licensed under AGPL-3.0 (Nano).